

Satellite observations of level 2 products over the Amazon rainforest during the August 15th-22nd fires from TROPOMI

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Abstract. The TROPOMI (TROPOspheric Monitoring Instrument) is on board the Copernicus Sentinel 5 Precursor (S5P) satellite. TROPOMI level 2 data products are generated within the Copernicus ground system. The data products contain information on the data quality for each TROPOMI ground pixel. We present data on the variations of levels of aerosol layer height (ALH), carbon monoxide (CO), formaldehyde (HCHO), methane (CH₄), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), total ozone column (O₃), and sulphur dioxide (SO₂) over the Amazon Rainforests before, during, and after the fires.

Introduction

During August 15th-22nd, 2019 major fires took place in the Brazilian Amazon Rainforests. Those fires mark 2019 as the most active fire year in the region in the last decade.

Total number of fires, 1 January - 29 August (1998-2019)

Source: National Institute for Space Research

Figure 1. amount of fires in the Amazon region per year since 1998. While these fires attracted extremely high media coverage, we can observe that the

Amazon has gone through much worse in the early 2000s.

Fire levels in the Amazon varies noticeably from year to year. Two major factors for the fires are drought and land clearing, the latter being far more prominent in the Amazon rainforests in general as well as in the 15th-22nd fires [Voiland, 2019]. Using TROPOMI, we were able to retrieve the levels of different Level 2 products over the region. **Aerosol Layer Height** product centers on retrieval of vertically localized aerosol layers in the free troposphere such as biomass burning aerosol, or volcanic ash plumes in layers for cloud-free scenes. **Carbon Monoxide** (CO) is important for our understanding of tropospheric chemistry, as it could be a major atmospheric pollutant. Combustion of fossil fuels and biomass burning are among the main sources of CO. While at northern mid-latitudes the combustion of fossil fuels is the main source of CO, biomass burning plays a big role in the region we are interested in [Reisen et al 2011]. TROPOMI observes the CO levels in the 2.3 μm spectral range of the shortwave infrared (SWIR) part of the solar spectrum. **Formaldehyde** (HCHO) is a principal intermediate in the oxidation of hydrocarbons in the troposphere. Oxidation of methane by the hydroxyl radical is the main source of HCHO in most of the troposphere. Formaldehyde is an intermediate gas in almost all

oxidation chains of non-methane volatile organic compounds (NMVOC), leading eventually to CO₂. Globally, augmentations of HCHO levels are the results of oxidation of higher NMVOCs emitted from fires, vegetation, traffic, and industrial sources. Our location is rich in vegetation; thus, variations of formaldehyde levels in our area of interest during our timeline are primarily related to temperature changes and fire events [Chance et al 2000]. **Methane** (CH₄) is the second most important contributor to the anthropogenically enhance greenhouse effect, after CO₂. TROPOMI monitors CH₄ abundances in the Earth's atmosphere using the SWIR channel. There are six major sources of atmospheric methane. These include natural wetlands, paddy rice fields, emission from livestock production systems, biomass burning, anaerobic decomposition of organic waste in landfills, and fossil methane emission due to fossil fuels' exploration and transportation. In our limited timeline, biomass burning is likely the primary factor of variations in the level of methane [Heilig, 1994]. **Nitrogen Dioxide** (NO₂) is an important trace gas in the Earth's atmosphere. It is present in both the troposphere and the stratosphere. Main sources of NO₂ are fossil fuel combustion and biomass burning as well as natural processes such as microbiological processes in soils, lightning, and wildfires [Reisen et al 2011]. The TROPOMI NO₂ processing system is based on the algorithm developments for the DOMINO-2 product and for the EU QA4ECV NO₂ reprocessed dataset for OMI. **Ozone** (O₃) is important for the radiation balance of Earth atmosphere. While in

the stratosphere, an ozone layer shields the biosphere from dangerous solar ultraviolet radiation, in the troposphere it acts as an efficient cleansing agent. However, at high levels it becomes harmful to humans, animals, and vegetation. Among causes of high level of ozone are sunshine, hot temperature, and high emissions of NO_x and VOC pollutants. **Sulphur Dioxide** (SO₂) impact ranges from short term pollution to effects on climate. SO₂ levels increase mostly from anthropogenic origin such as fossil fuel combustion at power plants and other industrial facilities, but also from volcanos. Increases in SO₂ negatively impact human health and air quality [Wang et al, 2018].

Data Gathering and Analysis

Figure 2. Latitude is between -9.38° and -7.04°. Longitude is between 71.31° and -6.761°. Coordinates are marked by the turquoise rectangle.

Using TROPOMI, we measured data on the aforementioned products. Once we had downloaded the data for the Amazon region, we zoomed in on this specific area using an algorithm that took into account the recommended levels that TROPOMI states should be ignored due to noise.

Figure 3. Levels of vertically integrated CO columns (mol m^{-2}). Grayed out areas are either out of the satellite's orbit or masked due to noise.

The difference from August 15th to 16th is striking. High levels of CO continue on the 17th but also decrease slightly from the 16th. On August 22nd and 23rd, levels of CO decrease, yet are still evident. By September 2nd, 11 days after the fires were over and in comparison to August 16th, levels are relatively low in the whole Amazon region. Rise in CO emissions is essential in the escalation of climate change and has a direct impact on expediting it through its major role in the destruction of tropospheric OH. [Urbanski, 2014]. Similarly to the rise of CO levels in the Amazon region during the fires, the levels of Aerosol

mid Height also vary significantly every day, peaking on August 18th.

Figure 4. Height at center of aerosol layer relative to geoid mean varies drastically over the ten days that span the fires. Levels begin to raise from August 16th

until a peak of 1380.636 meters on August 18th. August 20th data is intentionally ignored due to noise.

After applying recommended filtering given by TROPOMI, we created this graph that depicts the mean of the height at the center of aerosol layer relative to the geoid. the mean varies considerably from August 18th in which $\mu = 1380.636\text{m}$, to August 23rd, one day past the fires, on which $\mu=320.1\text{ m}$. The inevitable cause to the rise of aerosol mid height levels is the fires. Moreover, the spike in the data, followed by a hard decrease after the fires were over, suggest the existence of rain and an increase in atmospheric convection due to the fires.

Figure 5. Levels of air mass factor of Formaldehyde (mol m⁻²) averaged per day over the timespan of the fires.

Air mass factors (AMF) relate apparent column densities (ACD) to vertical column densities (VCD) through: $\delta = \text{ACD}/\text{VCD}$ Where δ represents the air mass factor. AMF is required to convert slant column densities (SCDs) to vertical column densities (VCDs); it depends on cloud properties, vertical profiles of HCHO, surface reflectance, aerosols, and observation geometry [H.-A. Kwon et al 2017]. The results of the air mass factor of HCHO range between 1.504 to 2.08 (mol m⁻²). The graph depicts an immediate increase from August 14th to August 15th, the day the fires started. Following it, there is a decay until August 20th trailed by a short increase

and again a decrease, as expected, on August 23rd, once the fires are no longer active [Palmer et al 2001]. Satellite HCHO column observations are sensitive to the changes in the atmospheric conditions, which are in turn impacted by massive fires. Hence, explaining the variations in the levels of HCHO AMF.

Figure 6. (a) Depiction of levels of column averaged dry air mixing ratio of methane on August 22nd (1e-9). (b) Graph of levels of Column averaged dry air mixing ratio of methane (1e-9), August 18th and 20th are missing due to masked data.

Our results of levels of column averaged dry air mixing ratio of methane vary between 1802-1838 (1e-9), however, we are missing data on two critical days. Moreover, the ratio of methane does not change extensively in our timespan, which makes it difficult to recognize the impact of the fires from the levels of column averaged dry air mixing ratio of

methane.

Figure 7. (a) Graph of total Ozone (O₃) column (b) Graph of total vertical column of Sulphur Dioxide (SO₂) (c) Graph of vertical column on Nitrogen Dioxide NO₂. All measurements are of (mol m⁻²). The X axis represents the day.

The graph of total Ozone **7 (a)** shows an increase starting on August 15th and ending on August 22nd, with some deviations. Increase in Ozone is linked to increases of both pollution and a variety of adverse health effects and is directly connected to the existence of biomass burning [Reisen et al, 2011]. Moreover, it is directly linked with climate change. Graph **7 (b)** represents the total vertical column of sulfur dioxide

for the polluted scenario derived from the total slant column, measured in mol m⁻². An immediate increase in the levels of SO₂ is noticed on the commencing day of the fires, on August 15th. However, an interesting decrease takes place immediately after the 15th, such that by August 17th the level of the total vertical column of sulfur dioxide for the polluted scenario derived from the total slant column is as it was before the August 15th fires started. While the main sources for SO₂ emissions are anthropogenic and not biomass burning, these results are still not what we had expected and should be explained [Lindfors, 2018]. Finally, the tropospheric vertical column of Nitrogen Dioxide, also measured in mol m⁻², appears to show a steady decrease, with some variations, from August 13th until August 23rd. Since the main source of NO₂ is the burning of fossil fuels and not biomass burning, we should not be surprised that we have not encountered a rise in the levels on NO₂. The decrease, however, could perhaps be explained by the increase of O₃.

Conclusions

The Amazon rainforests fires of August 15th-22nd were a negative impact on the air quality in the region and a catalyst for climate change. Our data shows the increase of CO, O₃, HCHO, and aerosol layer height. Moreover, while we do not see a clear increase in the levels of SO₂, CH₄, and NO₂, we do see intriguing variations. These variations are a testament to the impact of the fires in the region. They hint to the varying levels of the fires on each day, as well as on the existence of rain. This is

especially seen by the drastic changes in ALH. We must note that while the numbers of the fires were high, they were not the highest in the last decade. Furthermore, while the fires in the Amazon rainforests received immense media coverage, larger and equal-sized fires in Africa and Siberia took place at the same time [Pierre-Louis, 2019]. Moreover, neither of those locations were named “the Earth’s lungs”, a misleading term that ignores the fact that most of the Oxygen made by the Amazon rainforests is actually consumed by it [Nepstad, 2019]. The primary reason for why fires in the Amazon rainforest are dangerous is in fact climate change. Out of 10.7 Gigatons of carbon emitted to the atmosphere by human activities, 25-30% of it is absorbed thanks to photosynthesis [Le Quere, 2018]. Therefore, the vegetation in our world, and especially the tropical rainforests, is critical in decelerating climate change, which is mostly derived from emission of CO₂. 90% of CO₂ emissions are due to fossil fuels. The remaining 10%, however, come from biomass burning. Thus, fires in the Amazon rainforest turn rainforests from decelerators of climate change into accelerators of climate change.

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